

Climate Adaptation and Mitigation Behaviours Among Individuals and Households: Insights from the Sri Lankan Experience

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Abstract

Climate change presents significant challenges, making it essential to understand mitigation behaviors at both individual and household levels. This study explores behavioral attitudes toward climate change among households and individuals in the Colombo district, Sri Lanka. Three focus group discussions (FGDs) were conducted by the principal investigator in diverse settings, including high-income and low-income urban communities and rural areas, with eight purposively selected participants in each group. Semi-structured FGDs were used, and discussions were audio-recorded with participants' consent. The majority (58.3%) were men, and 41.7% were under 40 years of age. One-third had an educational level of a degree or higher, while 16.7% were unemployed. Thematic analysis identified seven key themes: perceptions of climate change and weather patterns, perceived causes of climate change, vulnerability and risk perceptions, individual attitudes toward climate mitigation, resistance to climate mitigation policies, skepticism toward individual efforts, and calls for collective action and education. While some individuals actively engage in climate-friendly behaviors, others feel their efforts are negligible compared to large-scale industrial pollution and government shortcomings. Despite skepticism and resistance, participants recognized the importance of education and collective action in addressing climate change. The study recommends implementing targeted awareness campaigns to bridge knowledge gaps, promoting community-led initiatives to enhance local engagement, and developing policy interventions that incentivize sustainable behaviors. Encouraging collaboration between government agencies, educational institutions, and local communities can foster long-term commitment to climate mitigation efforts.

Keywords: *adaptation strategies, behavioral attitudes, carbon footprint, climate change mitigation, greenhouse gases.*

Suggested citation: Kalubowila, K.C., & Arambepola, C. (2025). Climate Adaptation and Mitigation Behaviours Among Individuals and Households: Insights from the Sri Lankan Experience. *European Journal of Ecology, Biology and Agriculture*, 2(2), 96-105. DOI: 10.59324/ejeba.2025.2(2).09

Introduction

Climate change remains one of the most pressing global challenges of the 21st century, primarily driven by human activities that contribute to rising greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions. Addressing this issue is a key objective of the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development, which emphasizes reducing emissions while balancing environmental sustainability and economic growth across both developed and developing nations (Shaheen & Lipman, 2007; United Nations, 1992, United Nations, 2015; Hsiang & Kopp, 2018).

Public engagement and awareness are crucial in achieving this goal, particularly in promoting climate change mitigation at both the individual and household levels.

One of the most effective strategies for mitigating climate change is modifying behavior through public health interventions. Since households represent the fundamental unit of a community, targeting behavioral change at this level is both practical and cost-effective (Akhter & Malaviya, 2014). Within a household, members tend to adopt similar consumption patterns and lifestyles, making it an ideal setting for promoting low-carbon living. Encouraging sustainable household practices is therefore essential for achieving broader climate mitigation goals.

Previous studies suggest that increasing awareness of energy conservation can influence behavior and reduce energy consumption (Abrahamse et al., 2005; Prasad, Asa, & Hongyi, 2015). However, when responsibility is shared among individuals, personal accountability tends to diminish, reducing the long-term effectiveness of such initiatives. While Abrahamse et al. (2005) indicate that providing information alone may result in only short-term behavioral changes (Hope, 2016), fostering positive attitudes toward renewable energy and energy efficiency measures is more likely to encourage sustainable long-term practices such as cycling and the use of public transportation (Wallace et al., 2010). The Cognitive Consistency Theory suggests that attitudes strongly influence behavior (Darby, 1999), yet the relationship between attitudes, actions, and carbon emissions remains complex (Ueno et al., 2006). Understanding these behavioral attitudes is essential for shaping effective public health strategies to address climate change.

In developed countries, the concept of Zero Carbon Homes, where carbon dioxide emissions from energy use are minimized or offset, has already been incorporated into policy. However, this initiative has not yet gained traction in many developing nations (Georgiadou, 2014). Policies promoting Zero Carbon Home practices could significantly influence consumer behavior and energy consumption patterns (Kerkhof, Nonhebel, & Moll, 2009). While attitudes play a crucial role in shaping household energy use, there has been limited research on their impact on climate change mitigation in developing nations.

This study seeks to explore behavioral attitudes toward climate change mitigation in urban and rural households in Sri Lanka. The findings aim to provide valuable insights for policymakers in designing strategies to influence household energy consumption and offer a reference point for other developing nations with similar socio-economic contexts.

Methods

This qualitative study was conducted in 2018 in the Colombo district, the most densely populated district in Sri Lanka, encompassing diverse socio-economic backgrounds. The district consists of both urban and rural areas, classified based on the local government structure (Department of Census and Statistics, 2019). Purposive sampling was used to ensure representation from three distinct groups: urban dwellers from highly congested areas representing low-income urban communities, rural residents from regions with limited energy resources, and individuals actively engaged in climate change mitigation practices such as solar energy use, electric vehicle adoption, and waste recycling. Within each household, the individual most familiar with daily household activities was selected to obtain a detailed perspective on climate change mitigation behaviours. The selected participant was invited for the Focus group discussion (FGD). All efforts were taken to provide a conducive environment for discussions. With the help of a field health worker, a convenient place was arranged for each FGD, which ensured privacy and a relaxed environment with minimal disturbances for respondents to express their views. Informed verbal consent was obtained from all participants.

FGDs were conducted with eight participants per discussion by the principal investigator (PI) who was well-trained in qualitative data collection. To moderate the discussion, a semi-structured FGD guide was developed following a thorough literature review and expert opinion obtained from a panel of community physicians and experts in environmental science; and pre-tested among a group of residents to confirm whether the probes led to the anticipated range of responses. The discussions were recorded with the consent from all participants. The PI decided on when to stop the FGD at the point that no more themes were generated during the discussion. After completion of each FGD, the PI reviewed the recorded audios, after which data analysis was carried out through an iterative process of reading, coding, recoding, displaying, reducing and summarizing them into themes. This provided a detailed description of attitudes towards climate mitigation among residents in the district of Colombo.

The study was approved by Ethics Review Committee, Faculty of Medicine, University of Colombo, Sri Lanka.

Results

Three FGDs were conducted, involving 24 participants, following Mason's (2010) guidelines for determining the appropriate number of interviews. Among them, 58.3% (n=14) were male, while 41.7% (n=10) were under the age of 40. Additionally, 33.3% (n=8) held a degree or higher educational qualification.

The discussions generated several themes regarding behavioral attitudes toward climate change mitigation, which are presented below.

Perceptions of Climate Change and Weather Patterns

Most participants acknowledged that climate change is occurring in Sri Lanka, often linking it to observable changes in atmospheric conditions, such as increasing temperatures and extreme weather events. Many described experiencing hotter daytime temperatures, unpredictable weather patterns, shorter but more intense rainfall, and prolonged dry spells.

A 45-year-old rural resident shared:

"When I think about changes in the weather, the first thing that comes to mind is the increasing temperature. Compared to earlier times, the daytime feels much hotter. In the past, we never experienced floods in February and March, but now we expect heavy rains for shorter durations, followed by long dry periods. Even though the intensity of rainfall has increased, the number of rainy days seems to have decreased."

Further discussions revealed that climate change was perceived as a serious concern primarily by those who had personally experienced extreme weather events. Flood victims, for instance, viewed climate change as an urgent issue, while those who had not experienced such disasters showed less immediate concern. A flood victim from a low-income urban area expressed:

"We seem to be at the highest risk for flooding because we live in a highly populated area. Even a short period of rain is enough to cause flooding here."

Misperceptions about climate change were influenced by socio-cultural beliefs and media messages. A 33-year-old woman from a low-income urban community, who had been displaced by the 2005 tsunami, linked increased flooding to fate rather than human activities:

"Since moving here in 2005 after the tsunami, I've noticed more frequent floods and increased rainfall. But I think it's due to congestion in our area. People in other parts of the country don't experience this as we do. [Sighs] It feels like the bad effects of nature (karma) are following us."

Perceived Causes of Climate Change

While human activities are widely recognized as a major driver of climate change, awareness of these causes varied significantly among participants.

Some respondents, particularly those with a science background, identified rapid population growth as a key contributor due to increased demand for electricity, water, and fossil fuels. A 65-year-old teacher explained:

"The expansion of the population is responsible for climate change. More people mean increased electricity use and cutting down more trees to build houses."

However, many rural participants did not acknowledge human activities as a major factor. Some believed that nature operates independently of human influence, as stated by one rural resident:

"There is no relationship between people and nature. God made everyone and everything on Earth. How can people change the climate with the small amounts of carbon dioxide they release?"

Others attributed climate change to astrological or supernatural forces. A 54-year-old participant said:

"Climate change is happening due to the influence of stars. I don't believe it is related to science or karma. Therefore, even if we want to, we cannot change it. If we could alter the star patterns, we might be able to adjust the long-term weather patterns."

Scientific misconceptions were also prevalent. A 32-year-old businessman incorrectly associated climate change with atmospheric holes:

"Harmful rays, such as ozones, are coming into the air through the holes in the Earth."

Vulnerability and Risk Perceptions

Perceptions of personal risk from climate change influenced attitudes toward mitigation. Many participants underestimated their vulnerability, assuming that limited energy consumption or living in rural areas reduced their risk.

A 45-year-old housewife from a low-income urban area shared:

"We don't waste resources because we don't have money to buy things, so we are safe."

Similarly, many rural residents believed they were not at risk, perceiving climate change as a problem primarily affecting urban centers with heavy traffic and industrial emissions. A 53-year-old rural participant explained:

"Since we live away from the town, I don't think we are at risk. Unlike Colombo City, we don't experience heavy traffic. More vehicles in the city emit harmful gases, so they face the risk, not us. Likewise, we don't suffer from massive floods regularly."

Such misconceptions could lead to overuse of natural resources, while migration patterns based on perceived safety may contribute to increased urban congestion and vulnerability.

Individual Attitudes toward Climate Mitigation

Climate mitigation efforts often face barriers related to personal beliefs, financial limitations, and space constraints. Many participants hesitated to adopt energy-efficient appliances or reduce fossil fuel use, even when they acknowledged the importance of climate-friendly actions.

A university lecturer, however, described his commitment to climate mitigation through behavioral changes:

“I switched from using my car to cycling to reduce carbon emissions. As someone responsible for mitigating climate change, I also hope to educate others about the importance of these actions. Cycling has not only helped me reduce my carbon footprint but also allows me to enjoy the environment, lower my blood pressure, and reduce stress on traffic-heavy days. The only challenge I face is cycling in rainy weather.”

Some engaged in GHG reduction through renewable energy solutions, such as solar panels and electric vehicles. A 45-year-old man shared:

“I’m using an electric car. On my way to work, I have to drop my kids to two different schools in Colombo. As I am facing a huge traffic daily, I think electric car is the best option for me as well as to save the environment.”

Another participant added:

I have been using solar panels for nearly ten years. I think it is the most suitable way to reduce electricity cost.”

Resistance to Climate Mitigation Policies

While climate mitigation requires collective action, many participants distrusted government policies. A participant criticized Sri Lanka’s carbon tax, stating:

“I don’t accept the carbon tax. What has occurred here is that another tax has been added to the burden of vehicle users, which is an income generator to the government. Also, the government did not start the vehicle emission test with the aim of environmental protection, but simply to check the emission standards and to determine whether vehicles are within the government defined limits. This is one of the failures of the government, so my argument is to initiate some practical solution to save the environment”.

Skepticism and Fatalistic Attitudes toward Individual Efforts

Some participants were skeptical about their personal contributions to climate mitigation. A 32-year-old married woman with two children said:

“As factories release air pollutants and people cut down trees on a large scale without considering the environment or the future, what difference does my individual contribution make? My efforts are negligible in the grand scheme of climate change.”

Social status also influenced behaviour. A participant viewed cycling as socially undesirable:

“In Sri Lanka, cycling is often associated with poverty, or people assume I’m just being stingy. Why should I inconvenience myself when I own a car? Life is meant to be enjoyed. Besides, even if I cycle, I won’t stop climate change—so why go through all that trouble for the 60 or 70 years I’ll live?”

Call for Collective Action and Education

Effective climate mitigation requires not only government initiatives but also public support and awareness. A community leader emphasized self-reliance in addressing climate change:

“We should stand up on our own. We should teach or provide education to our people on how to reduce carbon emission rather than begging from others. We forgot or are about to forget to learn how to survive. Just receiving donations will make people kneel down”.

Discussion

The area of residence significantly influences people’s lifestyles, shaping their consumption patterns related to goods, services, food, travel, and energy use. These consumption behaviors are key contributors to household GHG emissions. Our study findings indicate that while both urban and rural residents in Sri Lanka are aware of climate change, they exhibit negative attitudes toward their role in its mitigation. This is reflected in their limited perception of vulnerability to its effects, insufficient knowledge, and

cultural misconceptions about its causes. Furthermore, skepticism toward technological solutions for mitigation and distrust in government-led initiatives further hinder proactive engagement in climate action.

Over time, global attention on environmental issues has increasingly shifted toward global warming (Sampei & Aoyagi-Usui, 2009). Countries experiencing distinct seasonal variations tend to be more conscious of climate change, as they observe noticeable temperature increases during both summer and winter (McElwain & Sweeney, 2003). In line with this, meteorological studies in Sri Lanka have also reported a distinct rise in both daytime maximum and nighttime minimum air temperatures (Basnayake, 2002). However, findings from the current study indicate that communities primarily associate climate change with rising daytime temperatures, suggesting greater concern over hot days rather than warmer nights.

Unlike countries with extreme seasonal fluctuations, Sri Lanka, being an equatorial island with a tropical climate, experiences relatively stable temperatures around 27°C throughout the year (Department of Meteorology, 2018). Consequently, temperature variations are not perceived as a direct consequence of climate change. However, the study findings suggest that public concern over climate change has intensified in response to the increasing frequency of natural disasters in recent years (Daily Mirror, 2017). Similar trends have been observed in both developed and developing countries, including Vietnam, Japan, several African nations, Bangladesh, Laos, and the Philippines (Toan et al., 2014; Gonzalez & da Silveira, 1997; Leiserowitz, 2005; Emch, 2008; Chaudhary & Bawa, 2011; Sampei & Aoyagi-Usui, 2009), where storms, floods, severe cold spells, and prolonged heat waves have been identified as major manifestations of climate change (Toan et al., 2014).

Climate change poses a universal threat, affecting every individual worldwide, with no one entirely spared. However, its impacts are not evenly distributed, disproportionately affecting certain communities based on geographic, economic, and social factors. Perceptions of climate risk vary across different sectors and societies, making mitigation efforts complex and, at times, frustrating for environmentalists and climate scientists. Findings from the current study reveal that individuals residing in rural areas perceive themselves to be at lower risk of climate change compared to urban dwellers. This belief stems from the perception that living away from urban centers reduces exposure to environmental hazards. Similarly, low-income urban communities associate their lower energy consumption with reduced climate impact. These attitudes appear to be influenced by the limited penetration of scientific knowledge on climate change within these communities. The study highlights the need to address misinformation, misconceptions, and unspoken assumptions about climate change. Achieving this requires clear, accessible, and targeted communication strategies to ensure that high-risk groups receive accurate and comprehensible information, ultimately fostering a more informed and proactive approach to climate change mitigation.

While astrology has been historically referenced in relation to natural events, there is no scientific basis for it influencing climate change. Climate patterns and changes are best understood through scientific principles, including meteorology, atmospheric physics, and environmental science. Despite this, astrological beliefs about climate change remain prevalent in some communities (Anderson & Bows, 2012). Scientific literacy has been shown to correlate strongly with higher levels of education, influencing individuals' understanding of climate change and its causes (Combest-Friedman, Christie & Miles, 2012). Similarly, findings from the current study indicate variations in climate change awareness and misconceptions across urban and rural populations, shaped by education levels and residential settings. Low-income urban communities with limited educational backgrounds were more likely to hold misconceptions and myths about the causes of climate change. Addressing these misunderstandings through targeted awareness campaigns and integrating climate science education into national policies will be essential for fostering informed decision-making and effective climate action.

In this study, residents actively engaged in climate change mitigation efforts, such as using solar power and electric vehicles, were included to explore how their attitudes toward environmental conservation might differ from those who are less involved. The negative attitudes toward climate change mitigation observed among urban slum communities may be attributed to their limited capacity to implement mitigation measures. This constraint is primarily influenced by household-level resources and decision-making power, which are often restricted among marginalized groups. In contrast, rural communities displayed neutral attitudes toward climate change mitigation. Many perceived the presence of high vegetation cover in their surroundings as a form of natural protection, leading to a false sense of security. As a result, they were less likely to take proactive measures to address climate change impacts. These findings highlight the need for targeted interventions that consider socioeconomic disparities and localized perceptions when promoting climate adaptation and mitigation strategies.

Although climate change is a global phenomenon, its adverse effects are more severely felt in developing countries due to their high dependence on natural resources and limited capacity to cope with climate variability and extreme events (United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change, 2007). Within these nations, economically disadvantaged populations are particularly vulnerable and are likely to bear the greatest burden in the future. To address this challenge, climate change mitigation should be promoted through behavioral shifts at both household and individual levels, aligning with the Zero Carbon Home concept. However, as highlighted by participants in our study, the practicality and cost-effectiveness of such measures must be carefully considered to ensure wider adoption. Governments, industries, and individuals can contribute to lowering costs and increasing accessibility to sustainable solutions. Key strategies include improving household energy efficiency, transitioning to alternative energy sources such as biofuels, and promoting large-scale tree planting. While these approaches offer long-term environmental benefits, they require significant effort and commitment to implement effectively (Akbari, 2002).

A carbon tax is a widely recognized economic tool designed to internalize the external costs of carbon emissions. By imposing a per-unit tax on pollutants, it serves as both an incentive for energy conservation and a mechanism to shift consumer demand toward cleaner, lower-emission energy sources (Harris, Roach & Anne-Marie, 2007). However, our findings revealed negative public attitudes toward government-imposed carbon taxes. In the context of a developing country, such a tax could only be effective if it is implemented transparently and reinvested in environmental sustainability initiatives. Otherwise, it risks being perceived as merely another revenue-generating mechanism that disproportionately burdens economically disadvantaged groups. Similarly, research has shown that eco-driving techniques, such as optimizing acceleration, maintaining steady speeds, and reducing idling, can decrease fuel consumption by up to 10%, making it a viable strategy for mitigating climate change (Barkenbus, 2010). Furthermore, such evidence should complement the local evidence identified on behavioural attitudes of citizens on climate change mitigation, when developing policies with the involvement of stakeholders; government, public institutions and private corporations.

Conclusions

Findings from this study highlight the diverse behavioral attitudes and varying perceptions of climate change vulnerability and causes among urban and rural residents. Negative attitudes were particularly linked to reluctance in adopting newer technologies for mitigation, emphasizing the challenges in promoting climate-friendly innovations.

Recommendations

To enhance climate change mitigation efforts, low-cost and practical interventions should be prioritized at the household level. Strengthening awareness, improving access to affordable green technologies, and integrating community-based solutions will be essential in fostering more sustainable and proactive climate actions across diverse populations.

Acknowledgements

The authors extend their sincere gratitude to all the residents who participated in this study for their time and valuable insights. We also appreciate the support of the Provincial and Regional Directors of Health Services for granting permission and facilitating the data collection process.

Author Contribution

All authors contributed to the initial discussions on the content and structure of the paper. KK drafted the first version of the manuscript. All authors participated in the review and editing of the first and subsequent drafts. All authors have read and approved the final manuscript.

Funding

Self-funded

Conflict of interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Ethics clearance

The study was approved by Ethics Review Committee, Faculty of Medicine, University of Colombo, Sri Lanka.

References

- Abrahamse, W., Steg, L., Vlek, C., & Rothengatter, T. (2005). A review of intervention studies aimed at household energy conservation. *Journal of Environmental Psychology*, 25(3), 273–291.
- Akbari, H. (2002). Shade trees reduce building energy use and CO₂ emissions from power plants. *Environmental Pollution*, 116, S119–S126. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0269-7491\(01\)00264-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0269-7491(01)00264-0)
- Akhter, S., & Malaviya, P. (2014). Carbon footprint analysis of rural households with respect to fuel and energy consumption in village Chak Chua of district Jammu, J & K. *Indian Journal of Science*, 10(26), 67–71.
- Anderson, K., & Bows, A. (2012). A new paradigm for climate change. *Nature Climate Change*, 2(9), 639–640.
- Barkenbus, J. N. (2010). Eco-driving: An overlooked climate change initiative. *Energy Policy*, 38(2), 762–769. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enpol.2009.10.021>

- Basnayake, B. R. S. B., Fernando, T. K., & Vithanage, J. C. (2002). Variation of air temperature and rainfall during Yala and Maha agricultural seasons. In *Proceedings of the 58th Annual Session of Sri Lanka Association for the Advancement of Science (SLASS)* (Section E, Vol. 1, p. 212).
- Chaudhary, P., & Bawa, K. S. (2011). Local perceptions of climate change validated by scientific evidence in the Himalayas. *Biology Letters*, 7(5), 767–770. <https://doi.org/10.1098/rsbl.2011.0269>
- Combest-Friedman, C., Christie, P., & Miles, E. (2012). Household perceptions of coastal hazards and climate change in the Central Philippines. *Journal of Environmental Management*, 112, 137–148. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2012.06.018>
- Daily Mirror. (2017). A visible solution to the disposal of garbage. Retrieved from <https://www.pressreader.com/>
- Darby, S. (1999). Energy advice—what is it worth. In *Proceedings of the European Council for an Energy-Efficient Economy Summer Study* (Paper III, Vol. 5, pp. 3–5).
- Department of Census and Statistics. (2019). *Household Income and Expenditure Survey – 2019*. Retrieved from <https://www.statistics.gov.lk/Resource/en/IncomeAndExpenditure/HouseholdIncomeandExpenditureSurvey2019FinalResults.pdf>
- Department of Meteorology. (2018). Climate of Sri Lanka. Retrieved from http://www.meteo.gov.lk/index.php?option=com_content&view=article&id=94&Itemid=310&lang=en
- Emch, M., Feldacker, C., Yunus, M., Streatfield, P. K., Dinh Thiem, V., Canh, D. G., & Ali, M. (2008). Local environmental predictors of cholera in Bangladesh and Vietnam. *The American Journal of Tropical Medicine and Hygiene*, 78(5), 823–832.
- Georgiadou, M. C. (2014). Future-proofed energy design approaches for achieving low-energy homes: Enhancing the code for sustainable homes. *Buildings*, 4(3), 488–519. <https://doi.org/10.3390/buildings4030488>
- Gonzalez, L. E., & da Silveira, P. (1997). The people's attitudes towards global environmental phenomena: A case study. *Climate Research*, 9(1–2), 95–100.
- Harris, J. M., Roach, B., & Codur, A. M. (2007). *The economics of global climate change*. Retrieved from [https://www.bu.edu/eci/files/2019/06/The Economics of Global Climate Change.pdf](https://www.bu.edu/eci/files/2019/06/The_Economics_of_Global_Climate_Change.pdf)
- Hope, S. A. (2016). *Knowledge, attitudes & practices study on climate change adaptation & mitigation in Guyana*. United Nations Development Programme. Retrieved from <https://www.undp.org/latin-america/publications/knowledge-attitudes-practices-study-climate-change-adaptation-mitigation-guyana>
- Hsiang, S., & Kopp, R. E. (2018). An economist's guide to climate change science. *Journal of Economic Perspectives*, 32(4), 3–32. <https://doi.org/10.1257/jep.32.4.3>
- Kerkhof, A. C., Nonhebel, S., & Moll, H. C. (2009). Relating the environmental impact of consumption to household expenditures: An input–output analysis. *Ecological Economics*, 68(4), 1160–1170. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolecon.2008.08.004>
- Leiserowitz, A. A. (2005). American risk perceptions: Is climate change dangerous? *Risk Analysis: An International Journal*, 25(6), 1433–1442. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1540-6261.2005.00690.x>
- Mason, M. (2010). Sample size and saturation in PhD studies using qualitative interviews. *Forum Qualitative Sozialforschung / Forum: Qualitative Social Research*, 11(3), Art. 8. <https://doi.org/10.17169/fqs-11.3.1428>

- McElwain, L., & Sweeney, J. (2003). Climate change in Ireland: Recent trends in temperature and precipitation. *Irish Geography*, 36(2), 97-111. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00750770309555815>
- Prasad, N. S., Asa, A. R., & Hongyi, X. (2015). Attitude and behavioral intention towards reducing carbon footprints in the environment: An empirical study of Fiji. *International Journal of Management Science and Business Administration*, 1(5), 21-30.
- Sampei, Y., & Aoyagi-Usui, M. (2009). Mass-media coverage, its influence on public awareness of climate-change issues, and implications for Japan's national campaign to reduce greenhouse gas emissions. *Global Environmental Change*, 19(2), 203-212. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gloenvcha.2008.10.005>
- Shaheen, S. A., & Lipman, T. E. (2007). Reducing greenhouse emissions and fuel consumption: Sustainable approaches for surface transportation. *LATSS Research*, 31(1), 6-20. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0386-1112\(14\)60179-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0386-1112(14)60179-5)
- Toan, D. T. T., Kien, V. D., Giang, K. B., Minh, H. V., & Wright, P. (2014). Perceptions of climate change and its impact on human health: An integrated quantitative and qualitative approach. *Global Health Action*, 7(1), 23025. <https://doi.org/10.3402/gha.v7.23025>
- Ueno, T., Sano, F., Saeki, O., & Tsuji, K. (2006). Effectiveness of an energy-consumption information system on energy savings in residential houses based on monitored data. *Applied Energy*, 83(2), 166-183. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2005.02.002>
- United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change. (2007). Climate change: Impacts, vulnerabilities and adaptation in developing countries. <https://unfccc.int/resource/docs/publications/impacts.pdf>
- United Nations. (1992). United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change. https://unfccc.int/files/essential_background/background_publications_htmlpdf/application/pdf/conveng.pdf
- United Nations. (2015). Transforming our world: The 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development. *UN General Assembly*. <https://sustainabledevelopment.un.org/post2015/transformingourworld>
- Wallace, A. A., Irvine, K. N., Wright, A. J., & Fleming, P. D. (2010). Public attitudes to personal carbon allowances: Findings from a mixed-method study. *Climate Policy*, 10(4), 385-409. <https://doi.org/10.3763/cpol.2009.0040>

